

DARTHs - Questionnaire report

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Are you

- A modeling system developer
- A modeling system users
- Both

If you are part of a community of model users/developers how big it is?

- Less than 5
- 5-15
- Larger than 15

Table 1: **Which is your modelling system name**

Model Name	Responses
CMF - Catchment Modeling Framework	2
eWaterCycle	1
FloodPROOFS/S3M	1
GEOframe	1
GEOtop	1
hydromt + wflow_sbm	1
HyM	1
HYPERstreamHS	1
Noah-MP in the Land Information System (LIS) framework	1
MISDc	1
mHM	1
Raven Hydrological Modelling Framework	1
saferplaces	1
SUMMA	1
SUPERFLEX	1
3GM	1

Select one answer about the modularity of your modeling system

- The modeling system is organized in models components that are connected together before the execution time with an appropriate scripting
- The code is organized in subroutines (or classes) but it is a bulk of code that manages data, processing and visualization together
- At present, the modeling system is not based on components but it could be easily refactored in components

Could you kindly explain why you/your community are not interested in modularize your modeling system? 0 Response

Table 2: Is the evolution of your modeling system totally in the hand of the original or restrict group of developers? If so, could you kindly explain why?

No this is not the case.

While the model is open source and so everyone can contribute, the development of the model is usually done with the help of the internal group of developers due to an initially steep curve (Fortran, etc.).

Everyone can contribute to extend, improve the model and its subroutines; in practice, due to initial difficulties steps (programming languages or understanding the structure of the model), the development of the model is usually done with the help of the internal group of developers.

I think so. You can have a look in the source code, but a change of the code is not possible. For me the code is very complex, so I would not know where to change something for the better.

No.

No, it is open source, but with supervised benchmarked realease from primary code maintainers.

No, all the codes are open access, in public repositories and anyone can contribute to them.

Everyone could in theory add something, in practice Philipp Kraft is the only person that maintains the project. I think this is mainly because it is his project and he has the biggest interest in it being developed further.

SuperflexPy is open source. Everybody can contribute to the development. Contributions need to still be evaluated and processed by the developers in order to be accepted. This workflow is intended to guarantee some quality control and consistency with the principles of the modelling framework.

Few users outside the group, development from outsiders mainly on model applications no contributions to the core. Not sure why: System not too well known, steep learning curve for the modular code, unwillingness to commit work to something not invented here.

No.

No open via GitHub.

Yes. It use used and developed only in my research group.

Restrict group.

No, it is open source.

No, Model development is completely open.

Original group, since many members, have changed the host research group/country. So it was difficult to modularize as it could not get tested on global scale.

The public version of the NASA LIS framework is implemented in GitHub and accessible.

Pull request are possible by the LIS community and monitored by the original group of NASA developers.

No the code is freely available on GitHub.

Table 3: Is the development of the modeling system carried out by a community of developers? If so, could you kindly list the rules for the governance of the community?

Yes, although not in its current stage this is envisioned for the future. The rules of governance are that components of the system should rely on open-source data. All citations and metadata should be included in the code and data.

The development is driven by internal developers. The main rule is to clone the original repository, develop the subroutines of the model with the standard of the programming languages (for example Fortran 2003 and Python 3.x) and create a new branch in the GitHub repository. All the rules are commonly available on the readme file in the GitHub repository. While this is now routinely done for Continuum, no branch has been created for S3M yet.

I do not know. I am just using the model.

There is a community of developers, but I am not part of this community.

Yes, but without formal rules for governance. Contributions to the trunk are vetted and carefully integrated so as not to introduce issues which would cause problems for operational users.

Yes, we are a great community and we clearly defined the rules for developers and users.

Not really.

The community of developers of SuperflexPy is composed by Marco Dal Molin, Dmitri Kavetski and Fabrizio Fenicia. Marco Dal Molin is in charge of the end product. He manages the website, documentation, Python codes, and deals with the community of users. Dmitri Kavetski and Fabrizio Fenicia are involved at a more conceptual level. In particular, they contribute to the the general principles of the modelling framework.

Currently not, but that is the goal and we already have rules in place that are oriented on general contribution rules in other Open Source projects.

Currently no formal governance.

No.

Restricted.

Yes, there is a GIT system. However, the model has weak governance.

Standard GitHub branching strategy. Raise issues, branch, make changes, make a pull request, independent code review, merge. Most discussion on GitHub.

It was developed as different components by different members and then merged to perform as single routine, so each component had one leader who was responsible to coordinate and manage.

This is reported in the "Contributing Guidelines of LIS": We welcome Pull Requests to LISF that add new features, enhance existing capabilities, and fix bugs! BUT, we ask that you first open an Issue (and, before that, a Discussion) so that we are aware of your intentions and have an opportunity to provide our feedback. Before beginning to work on your contribution, please review our Working with GitHub document for more information about our GitHub practices and a step-by-step guide to submitting a Pull Request. By contributing to the LISF repository, unless you explicitly state otherwise, you agree that your contribution will be licensed under the LISF Licence, which is under Apache Licence 2.0 <https://github.com/NASA-LIS/LISF/blob/master/LICENSE.txt>

No, it has been developed by our research group with some contributions from other researchers.

Table 4: **How can you contribute to the development of the modelling system?**

Contributions can be made through the GitHub repository. The protocol is that contributors create a pull request and the code is then reviewed by the development team before merging with the main branch.

Generally, based on the research purposes, everyone can clone the repository of the model and change, modify, extend and improve the subroutines and the functions.

By asking question and giving hints to the developer of the system.
In connection with the developing community

fork on SVN/raise issues on forum or TRAC page

By implementing new components and/or testing/debugging and eventually improving already existing ones

GitHub, simply send a pull request.

Pull requests on GitHub

Issues, pull requests, direct communication

For example through GitHub.

GitHub

I am, the main developer

Coding

Making a fork on git and then merging his developments.

Fork on GitHub, raise an issue, and make a pull request.

Depending on the aim of the model and background expertise

Developing new subroutines (i.e., for assimilation of new satellite products), improving observation operators for data assimilation, developing additional options to run the land surface models (i.e. improving irrigation schemes), fixing bugs, improving the documentation (it is difficult to find the needed information to understand the structure of the framework).

Being freely available via GitHub.

Table 5: **Can the modelling system be tested by third parties? If so, how?**

Yes, we have created a server (hpc-cloud) where eWaterCycle can be deployed. Third parties can use their own environment to test the system. This has been demonstrated with our latest GMD publication. Reviewers received their own environment to test the system.

Yes; the modelling system is completely open in the GitHub repository. No case study is provided, but we are working on that.

I think so. It's a free software package for python programming.

Open source model that can be tested by everyone

Tutorials and example models readily available online for testing. Also, it is open source, so users could implement unit testing if desired.

Yes, anyone can download both the codes and the projects, with test cases.

Not sure what this question is asking for.

It is open source, with a GNU Lesser General Public License

Code and binaries freely available with very little effort for installations

Yes. Download and follow the instructions to run it.

Yes.

Yes by contacting my research group.

Yes.

yes is open source.

yes we have a suite of test cases.

Yes, if they contact us.

The LIS framework can be accessed through GitHub: <https://github.com/NASA-LIS/LISF>.

Yes.

Table 6: **Do you, or your community, use a repository like GitHub? If so, which one? Is it publicly available?**

Yes we use a publicly available GitHub repository for code. Zenodo repository for storing data. Publicly available DockerHub were model instances can be downloaded.

GitHub; the repository of the model is public and freely available: <https://GitHub.com/c-hydro/>.

GitHub; the repository of the model is public and freely available.

I'm not using it now, but there is the plan to start using it soon.

Yes and public available.

We use an SVN repository hosted by the Canadian National Research Council (NRC), which can be accessed simply by signing up. We will likely move to GitHub in near future.

Yes, we use GitHub, publicly available.

<https://GitHub.com/philippkraft/cmfi>.

GitHub, which is publicly available.

GitHub <https://GitHub.com/philippkraft/cmfi>, public repository.

Yes, GitHub, Yes.

Yes GitHub.

No.

GitHub private.

<https://GitHub.com/geotopmodel/geotop>.

Yes, GitHub. The repository is public.

Yes GitHub.

Yes GitHub.

Yes GitHub.

Table 7: How do you, or your community, record the setup of the modeling system simulations for reproducibility purposes?

The ultimate test for reproducibility purposes is to run the model system from start to finish in a single JuPyter environment. This include forcing generation, model runs, and analyses. Another user runs this code to verify the reproducibility.

Examples of setup files are provided on the GitHub repository, along with code to generate input data with standardized formats. No case study is provided, but we are working on that.

A dataset to test and reproduce the results is available on GitHub into a dedicated repository.

Tracking via git and clear documentation in institutional wiki.

We have a regular benchmarking process against 30+ existing model implementations to ensure backward compatibility. The SVN supports versioning, and we have regular numbered releases.

We use public repositories for the projects such as OSF, GitHub and Zenodo.

<https://philippkraft.GitHub.io/cmfi/>

We collect a library of case studies, which can be downloaded and used for reproducibility.

The setup is done in code and can be recorded with standard code repositories, like git.

We have done a poor job in the past of doing that. But for future publications we strive to make configuration files as well as inputs for specific experiments available. Possibly even through software containers that contain everything to rerun the experiments.

Version numbering, releases etc

By saving in one folder all the input, the code and the output. All the methods are shared in papers. We do not share up to now raw data or the code itself.

Yes.

Yes, there is a Travis and Testing system implemented.

Full details are in our model workflows paper: <https://www.essoar.org/doi/10.1002/essoar.10509195.1>

Shared over internal server of the research group

It is not done, not yet.

How do you interact with the modeling system?

- By using a software specifically implemented to interact with the modeling system.
- By using a service API (Application Programming Interface) to perform a machine-to-machine interaction with a given model implementation which runs on a specific server
- By using a resource oriented interface (API) which directly access to the model itself and not to a given (fixed) model implementation/configuration
- I do not know this detail of the modeling system
- Other
 - no interface
 - Unclear question. I'm a computer scientist by training and do not understand what the question is targeting.
 - It is necessary to build a Python script that defines the model configuration. The Python scripts makes use of a library of SuperflexPy components.
 - we support direct interaction via text-based model input files, but the community has also developed python-based API and R libraries to support interaction. Both text and API access provide ability to manipulate model configuration completely.
 - By using a software specifically implemented to interact with the modeling system and by using a service API (Application Programming Interface) to perform a machine-to-machine interaction with a given model implementation which runs on a specific server. We take advantage of Julia, exe, BMI.

Where the modeling system runs?

- The modeling system runs on a specific computer and cannot be moved or executed on a different machine.
- The modeling system can be moved and executed on a machine that is suitable for a specific use case as a service callable from a client.
- You have at least a configuration of your system that runs automatically on the cloud using remote resources without your specific intervention.
- I do not know this detail of the modeling system
- Other
 - The model runs in Python, and can be run on any machine that has Python and the required libraries installed
 - The model can be executed on any computing platform providing a C++11 compiler and Python. Runs from Laptop to HPC. Containerized run possible.
 - Compile and run

Table 8: **Could you kindly explain which technologies do you use?**

We use a Dutch supercomputer (Snellius) and a German supercomputer (Mistral) for compute intensive model runs. In addition, we spawn a HPC server for lesser

The system uses a group of virtual environments and bashscripts to configure all the preprocessing, running and post-processing tools; these configuring tools are freely available in the GitHub repository.

To run the model over the common servers, the system uses a group of virtual environments and bash scripts to configure all the preprocessing, running and post-processing tools; these configuring tools are freely available in the GitHub repository; to run the model in a cloud system, the preprocessing, the runner and the post-processing tools are configured using both Docker and tools for orchestrating the workflow.

Linux or Windows cluster, Cloud/kubernetes, and Laptop.

The models could run on Linux system over servers. However parallelization is limited. There have been implemented R and Python packages to facilitate interaction with the code.

<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/geotopbricks/index.html> There are operational, real time implementation of the model. <https://www.mysnowmaps.com/en/>

Modeling system capabilities

- The modeling system allows the user to change its structure to test different modeling solution
- The modeling system includes a standard way to estimate error of forecasting
- None of the above
- You can run the model in different configurations in terms of scale and input details and parameterizations

Table 9: Could you kindly explain how the user can modify the modeling solutions? The user can chose among pre-defined modeling solutions or she/he is able to easily add her/his modeling solution?

- The user is able to add a modeling solution. This is not an easy process as it requires knowledge of Docker and the Basic Modeling Interface.
- We as a system provide out of the box Jupyter Notebooks that run an experiment from start to hydrograph. Users can select different regions of interest, various hydrological models, forcing data sources. Essentially we leave it up to the user to experiment whilst being impartial to the data or model he or she wants to use.

The model and its relative tools can be configured using the configuring files in json or ascii format. The users can select between some pre-defined process description (two different ways to compute evapotranspiration and two different ways to model the runoff propagation).

The modelling system is quite free. The user can implement as many different models as imaginable and doable.

The model, including the representation/algorithm used for each hydrologic process, how these processes connect together, which algorithms are used for routing/orographic correction/forcing estimation, how lakes/wetlands are handled, where and when specific processes are valid, etc, are all controlled via entries in the text-based input. Users may also use 'template' files which define pre-defined modelling solutions.

Both cases are possible: there are a lot of pre-defined modelling solutions but thanks to the easiness of the DSL used by OMS3, anyone can easily add his/her own modelling solution.

The user needs to define the model structure by prescribing the components and their connectivity. The definition of the model structure is done by a Python script in a prescribed way. SuperflexPy is just the hydrological model. No visualization or calibration options are included. These are available through independent external packages. The documentation explains how to link the hydrological model to some of these external packages. For calibration, for example, the model is seen by external software as an objective function, which is a function of the parameters.

The model is setup by connecting single, predefined equation blocks to an ODE to simulate water and solute fluxes in landscapes.

Both

There are multiple pre-defined model structures. It is also possible for a model developer to write code to include a new modelling option (this has been done by some users).

Use of Earth Observations (EO) data

Use of Earth Observations (EO) data

- The modeling system uses EO data systematically
- The modeling system does not use EO data

Table 10: **Could you kindly explain which EO data do you use?**

This is up to the user. The methods we apply for preprocessing of forcing data are applicable to EO data. If a user wants to include EO data in the experiment this is up to the user. Therefore I would not say that we apply it systematically.

Snow cover area and snow depth.

Precipitation, evapotranspiration, soil moisture, snow cover area and snow depth, LAI datasets.

Rain and Weather data

Precipitation, Temperature

Raven supports use of both gridded and point meteorological observations as forcing input. Raven can also ingest continuous or irregular state observations such as streamflow, soil moisture or SWE which are used to evaluate and report model fit to these observations. Land cover/soils/topographic data are typically used to classify the landscape. Raven also supports observations of vegetation or land use change over time.

We generally use the weather forcings data

I am not exactly sure about the meaning of EO data. Model realisations of CMF do not have a fixed data access module and can instead be connected to online and offline datasources of any kind. Data that have been used in the past: DWD (German Weather Service) climate data, data from the Schwingbach Observatory, GRDC data, runoff data from local authorities, own observations

Modis, vito landcover, MERIT hydro etc see imhoff et al 2020 and eilander et al. 2021

ground data, weather forecast. All have to be preprocessed

We use time invariant (or slowly varying) geophysical variables such as vegetation, soils etc. as part of the model spin up. We use output from atmospheric models as part of developing the model forcing data, e.g., see <https://essd.copernicus.org/articles/13/3337/2021/>
<https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/bams/aop/BAMS-D-21-0106.1/BAMS-D-21-0106.1.xml>
EO used to update model states (data assimilation) are separate from the model.

I am using backscatter observations from Sentinel 1, assimilated into Noah-MP, through a backscatter observation operator being the Water Cloud Model.

Satellite precipitation, evaporation and soil moisture through data assimilation.

Table 11: **How do you use EO data? Do you use them to drive the simulations or to calibrate/validate the model?**

Both. For example, we can use EO data for data assimilation (e.g. soil moisture). or snow state validation of a hydrological model. Again we leave this up to the user. Currently we stop at the first hydrograph as to not influence the users modelling decisions.

We use EO data for assimilation purposes.

Precipitation is always used as input. Evapotranspiration can be used as input or for calibration. Soil moisture can be assimilated or used for calibration. Snow cover area/snow depth are used for assimilation. LAI is used as input.

It used to drive the simulation.

Both. Raven also supports basic data assimilation via direct insertion or state nudging, and will in the near future support EnKF data assimilation.

Both

Build model hypotheses, drive the simulation, model calibration, result validation

For a priori estimate parameters, validation, driving (e.g. rainfall products)

all

EO are used for model forcing. EO are also being used for model evaluation, but this work is not very mature. EO are also being used for data assimilation. This work is also not very mature.

I assimilate the EO in the model to update both surface soil moisture and leaf area index.

Input data for calibration. Through data assimilation.

Methods of modeling

- The modeling system uses mainly Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs)
- The modeling system uses mainly Partial Differential Equations (PDEs)
- The modeling system uses both PDEs and ODEs
- The modeling system uses classical statistical methods
- The modeling system contains tools for machine learning analysis side by side with other modeling paradigms.
- Other:
 - The system itself does not manipulate models. We use the Basic Modelling Interface to interact with models that have various numerical implementations. This can range from a simple statistical method, to numerical solutions, to machine learning models.

Please indicate which are the modeling paradigms placed side by side with tools for machine learning. 0 Response

High Performance Computing (HPC) facilities

- The modeling system uses multicores.
- The modeling system uses multiple CPUs.
- The code is structured for using HPC.
- The modeling system is not parallelized at all and does not use HPC.
- The modeling system uses GPUs.
- An infrastructures takes care of parallelization to send the model on the cloud which is transparent to the developer/user.
- The modeling system uses distributed computing on the cloud.

About input-output (IO) does your model use standard file format

- .csv
- GRIB
- NetCDF
- HDF
- Apache arrow
- Other

- json
- This is independent of the hydrological model and it is responsibility of the user
- The model itself is format agnostic, every IO system usable from Python can be used. GRIB and Apache Arrow are possible, yet not used until now.

About input-output (IO) on average which is the size of the IO for the whole model

- Less than 1 GB
- 1-10 GB
- 10-100 GB
- Larger than 100 GB

About input-output (IO) on average which is the size of the IO for one file?

- Less than 1 GB
- 1-10 GB
- 10-100 GB

Table 12: **Please indicate which is on average the simulation time span and its time step**

On the I/O operations and time span. This is completely up to the user. When a user considers a vector-based model the I/O will be very small. When a fully distributed hydrological model is applied the I/O is large. Similarly this is the case for the simulation time span and time step.

Very variable, from hours to decades. Time step is usually hourly, but it is flexible.

The average simulation time depends by the domain size and by the length of the simulation; the mainly used time-step is 1 hour.

Raven has been deployed for 150-year simulations and for 7-day forecasts. It is typically used at daily or hourly time steps, but supports global time steps as small as one minute, and some algorithms use internal sub-stepping. The most standard applications would be ~30 year daily simulations or, in forecasting operations, ~15 day hourly simulations. Execution times on order of seconds to minutes.

5 minutes, hourly

Flexible

The SuperflexPy uses the Numba library, which compiles the Python code. For example, as a broad illustration of runtimes on a standard laptop, calibration of a HYMOD-like SuperflexPy model to observed daily data, requiring 1000s of model runs each with 1000 time steps, takes a few seconds with the Numba implementation compared to a couple of minutes with native Python execution.

Time span: Days to decades, time step: ms to day

Depends on the experiment. Ranging from minutes to weeks.

Varies per application (also file sizes) Model can be setup and run for single basin or continents at 1-2 km² or less

Daily, one minute

5 min

Usually, time span is several years, time step hourly, calculation time a few days.

These answers are for global simulations. Typically we run SUMMA for 40 years at hourly time steps.

About input-output (IO) do you adopt a naming convention for variables?

- BIM
- CF
- None
- Not sure about any of the acronym
- Other:
 - The output is user defined, hence the users can adopt any variable ontology they want
 - A custom one

For pre and post processing data analysis which languages or software do you use?

- Python
- Matlab
- R
- Panoply
- ncViewer
- QGIS
- Other

– cdo,nco

– We have an online user interface for visualizing output:

<http://raven.uwaterloo.ca/RavenView/RavenView.html>

Do you use techniques of literate computing within your modeling system workflow?
Such as Jupyter or Mathematica Notebooks, what else?

- Jupyter Notebooks
- Other
 - Sphinx with Docstrings and tools for model setup inspection
 - none
 - atom
 - R markdown files

What are the current modeling system limitations?

What are the current modeling system limitations?

- Usability
- Flexibility
- Scalability
- No limitations

Table 13: Could you kindly explain in more detail on the limitation of the modeling system and which are the most urgent to fix?

The current limitation is the ease at which models can be added to the system. This requires knowledge of Docker and BML. This process will be improved in the near future by providing adequate documentation.

The next development will be the parallelization of the model to run it on the HPC.

If the system is too detailed or too big, the modelling time is very long or the CPU does not allow the computation.

The primary limitation is the learning curve. The other key limitation (not included in the list above) is in supporting increasingly complex physics.

We are trying to simplify the initial setup of the modelling system and we need to increase our community of developers and users. But we are on our way.

Not sure how to answer the above question. We tried to find a balance between usability and flexibility. Therefore, there are certainly flexibility and usability limitations. See response to the last question.

Modular modelling systems have a steep learning curve, better documentation can help, but there is still quite an effort to start. The scalability issues would need to be addressed by competent numerical mathematicians, but a modular system can never be as optimized as a fixed one.

Better documentation of workflows.

Parallel computing/MPI (in progress) Adding process formulations

It depends on the purpose.

The code needs to be restructured to be modular. It needs also a better separation of I/O from computation. It needs full parallelization. See here <https://iris.sissa.it/handle/20.500.11767/86154#.XEXz0sZ718w> We are currently working on improving usability through better documentation and a diverse set of test cases. We are working on improving flexibility through better design templates. We are working on improving scalability through work on improved methods to solve the model equations and improved parallelization methods.

Difficult to apply the model to small basin at resolution higher than 1 Km considering that the input data have generally coarse spatial resolution.

For the purpose for which the model has been developed, it is fine. A modular structure can help its usability and flexibility.

Table 14: Which strategies do you/your community adopt to improve open science paradigm? For instance do you/your community offer documentation, tutorials to ease the use of your modeling system to other researcher? Do you/your community organize workshop, courses to present your model?

The eWaterCycle system will be adopted as a teaching tool at various universities in the Netherlands. The system is completely open-source and advocates reproducibility of science. The documentation that includes Jupyter Notebooks is available online.

We offer documentation and an user manual

<https://gmd.copernicus.org/preprints/gmd-2021-92/gmd-2021-92.pdf>.

We are also planning to organize workshops.

We offer the documentation over the readthedocs platform; e-learning courses have been developed for users and are offered in different applied projects that support hydrometeorological offices in developing countries.

Open source model and open GitHub.

Raven has documentation (240+ pg manual), 6 extensive tutorials, and an online user's forum.

We regularly use Raven in our graduate courses, but also offer Raven short courses to professionals (2-3/year since 2016)

We do offer, documentation, tutorials with videos, we organize courses, workshops at conferences, we are always available to welcome new modellists :)

We have an online documentation and tutorial. We also use the software in our summerschools or hydrological modelling lectures (such as at TU Delft).

- Code and binary published under a FOSS approved licence: tutorials available, API documentation available, and example setups available.

Documentation and tutorials yes. Workshops not yet but planned in the future.

Yes all

None

We offer documentation and a mailing list.

<https://GitHub.com/geotopmodel/geotop/tree/v2.2.1-old-master/doc>

<https://groups.google.com/g/geotopusers> In the past, we organized courses and workshops.

We are looking to access HCP expertise to refactor the code.

We do have documentation and we are developing a library of test cases. There is much more that we can do to develop tutorials and workshops.

Other comments or remarks not covered in the previous questions? Perhaps one aspect to make clear also in the commentary, which I have read and is very interesting, is to mention that there is a tradeoff between usability and flexibility. As we write in our SuperflexPy paper: "the intended flexibility of a framework may come at the expense of ease of use, similar to how computer languages have varying degrees of abstraction from the hardware behavior. Implementing a practical flexible framework therefore requires careful code design, experimentation, and, inevitably, some compromises." The HESS commentary points on generality, but such tradeoff between generality and ease of use is not fully covered. Finding the right balance is the key of success, and this requires making some specific choices.